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Conceptual Framework for Understanding Commonalities and Differences in Extreme Political Content Using Misinformation on Different Social Media Platforms

Work package 1– Deliverable 1.2

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Lead beneficiary: Aarhus University

Authors: Chiara Caterina Arena, Benjamin Nangle, Tania Azadi, & Leen d’Haenens

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1. Executive Summary

Extreme political content increasingly circulates on social media platforms in forms that fall below the thresholds that trigger platform moderation or legal intervention, yet still contribute to polarisation, the erosion of institutional trust, and shifts in the boundaries of acceptable public discourse. Crucially, such content often operates through mechanisms of misinformation and disinformation, where misleading, unverifiable or strategically framed information is embedded within narratives that are difficult to categorise as explicitly false or harmful. This blurring of boundaries complicates both conceptualisation and governance. This report addresses these challenges by examining socially unacceptable extreme discourse (SUEDs) at the intersection with information disorder. It proceeds in two parts: a scoping review mapping the state of the field, and a case study demonstrating the practical limits of existing definitional frameworks when applied to content that is deliberately designed to evade classification.

The scoping review identifies six recurring definitional clusters across the research literature: hate speech and discriminatory rhetoric, incitement to violence, dehumanisation and othering, conspiracy narratives, polarising and populist rhetoric and extremist ideological narratives. These categories are overlapping and are contested, as no unified definition has achieved cross-jurisdictional or cross-disciplinary consensus. Research methods range from large-scale computational approaches, including keyword classifiers and large language models, to qualitative discourse analysis and reflexive thematic analysis. Computational methods offer scale and replicability but are structurally limited in their capacity to detect content that operates through implication, coded language and cumulative framing. Qualitative approaches offer interpretive depth but present challenges of scalability and generalisation. The most consequential forms of extreme discourse are consistently those that prove most resistant to detection by existing tools.

The case study examines 40 German-language YouTube vodcasts published between December 2024 and August 2025, comprising over 50 hours of content from AfD politicians, Identitarian activists, and alternative media figures. Analysis identifies three primary mechanisms through which extreme political content circulates in long-form video without triggering moderation thresholds. Institutional delegitimation systematically portrays media, academia, courts, and civil society organisations as captured by hostile elite interests, constructing an alternative information environment in which far-right actors present themselves as the sole reliable sources. Statistical weaponisation deploys selective demographic data, crime statistics, and pseudo-scientific projections to normalise extreme narratives as empirical common sense. Deniability engineering substitutes euphemistic language, cultural framing, and centrist self-positioning for explicitly prosecutable expression, rendering individual statements formally defensible while their cumulative effect reconstructs extremist logic. Interestingly, 90 percent of videos in the sample include explicit meta-commentary on these strategies, confirming that the patterns observed reflect deliberate strategic production.

Together, the scoping review and case study support four conclusions with direct policy relevance. First, existing definitional frameworks are insufficient for governing the most

consequential forms of extreme online content, which are designed to circulate within definitional gaps rather than to violate explicit thresholds. Second, content format is an independent governance variable: long-form video affords strategic repertoires that short-form content cannot accommodate, and moderation frameworks calibrated to short-form platforms transfer poorly. Third, the deliberate character of mainstreaming strategies is empirically documented, with implications for how platform responsibility and regulatory intent should be assessed. Fourth, effective detection and governance require analytical approaches capable of evaluating cumulative effect across content rather than individual statements in isolation.

The report recommends that policy and platform governance frameworks develop cumulative effect analysis tools, introduce format-specific moderation criteria for long-form content, recognise explicit discussion of boundary-shifting strategies as a potential indicator of strategic content production, and combine qualitative interpretive analysis with computational detection to identify patterns that keyword-based systems are structurally unable to capture. Attention should be paid to forms of misinformation and disinformation that are embedded in or co-evolve with such content, including misleading framing, selective use of evidence, and narratives that are difficult to classify as explicitly false yet contribute to the cumulative effects of socially unacceptable extreme discourse.

2. About DEMINE

Globalisation and immigration have altered intercommunity relations, leading to a rise in intergroup conflict marked by discrimination against diverse minorities. This has given way to various forms of radicalisation and extremism, spanning religious, political and xenophobic spectrums worldwide. Globalisation and immigration strain social cohesion (shared public values, group norms, guiding principles) in numerous countries. While individual attitudes may not have shifted significantly, the prominence of migration in public discourse and the polarisation of public opinion have increased substantially. As a result, a divided public opinion has become more overtly hostile towards migration.

The DEMINE (DEaling with conflicts related to MIgration: NEgotiating social cohesion through communication) European Joint Doctorate (DN-JD) network is a collaborative effort across disciplines. Its primary goal is to enhance Europe's capacity to address a significant challenge: the rise of various forms of radicalisation and extremism that pose a threat to social cohesion. Through a combination of inter-sectoral mobility and a balanced blend of research and transferable competences, DEMINE develops a much-needed framework on the role and interplay of interpersonal and mediated communication in intergroup relations and conflict related to migration and globalisation, ultimately contributing to social cohesion. DEMINE has crafted a comprehensive research and training programme to examine the complex relationships between various forms of communication, including traditional media, social media, and interpersonal interactions. This programme aims to understand how various communication channels shape individual attitudes and beliefs regarding migration, as well as their impact on intergroup dynamics (social cohesion), especially within the broader context of political and societal polarisation, and the processes of radicalisation, with a specific focus on migration-related aspects.

DEMINE Educational Goals

- Train nine doctoral candidates to become the next generation of interdisciplinary researchers skilled in digital methods, participatory community research, and the evaluation of intergroup conflicts.
- Equip candidates with advanced theoretical and practical knowledge, focusing on strategic analysis, community-based participatory youth work, and open-source intelligence techniques.
- Develop transferable skills such as self-management, inter-sectoral collaboration, and innovation-oriented thinking to prepare candidates for both academic and non-academic careers.
- Promote interdisciplinary and international mobility, enabling candidates to apply their research findings in real-world contexts and contribute to professional fields ranging from strategic analysis to media production.

DEMINE Research Goals

- Identify and analyse the differences and similarities across various forms of socially unacceptable, extreme discourse, particularly related to migration, at the intersections of politics, media, and interpersonal communication.
- Investigate the impact of extreme discourse on individual attitudes and beliefs, with a specific focus on adolescents and vulnerable populations, while understanding the socio-demographic and psychological factors influencing susceptibility.
- Develop countermeasures to empower adolescents, news media producers, and political actors to mitigate the societal impact of divisive discourse, fostering social cohesion and reinforcing democratic principles.
- Provide a nuanced, cross-cultural, and interdisciplinary understanding of the mechanisms of polarisation and radicalisation to inform effective strategies and policy interventions.

By integrating these educational and research goals, DEMINE aims to enhance Europe's capacity to address the growing societal challenges linked to migration, fostering resilience and inclusivity in an increasingly polarised world.

DEMINE Consortium

DEMINE consists of three academic partners namely, KU Leuven, Aarhus Universitet, and Università Degli Studi di Padova as well as nine non-academic partners including OCAM-OCAD, City of Mechelen, Textgain, The Migration Policy Group, Refugees Welcome, Institut for Menneskerettigheder, Stichting Bellingcat, Verwey-Jonker Institute, and Hannah Arendt Institute.

The DEMINE consortium will train nine doctoral candidates (DCs) within a cross-disciplinary and international environment, giving them the opportunity to network, study and collect data in Western, Northern, Southern and Eastern Europe (see secondments) in collaboration with academic and non-academic experts, with ample opportunities to develop transferable skills such as technology literacy, adaptability (i.e., not feeling helpless in the face of change), strong

communication skills, and ability to work in a team, in a dependable and well-organised fashion.

3. Introduction

This report develops a conceptual framework for understanding socially unacceptable extreme discourse (SUED) as it circulates across social media platforms. Extreme discourse extends well beyond content that meets legal definitions of hate speech or incitement to violence. It encompasses a wider range of communication that promotes extreme ideological positions, undermines democratic norms, erodes institutional trust, and contributes to the radicalisation of communities, often through content that appears ambiguous, moderate, or factual on its surface. Such discourse frequently intersects with forms of misinformation and disinformation, including misleading framing, selective or decontextualised evidence, and the strategic blending of factual and unfactual claims, which together make harmful narratives more difficult to identify and contest. Discourse glorifying far-right historical figures, framing demographic change as civilisational threat, or constructing in-group identity through the exclusion of out-groups may carry significant radicalising potential. Platform logics, including algorithmic amplification, financial incentives, and content recommendation architectures, further shape how such content reaches audiences and how communities form around it. The definitional and methodological challenges involved in identifying, classifying, and responding to this content are substantial and are examined in the review that follows.

Responding effectively to extreme political content on social media requires shared, operational definitions of what that content is. The boundaries of extreme political discourse are, however, complex and contested. Platforms, regulators, legal systems and researchers operate with divergent frameworks, and the practical challenge is compounded by the fact that the most consequential content is often the least explicitly harmful. Governance capacity depends directly on definitional clarity; where definitions are unstable or deliberately circumvented, regulatory and platform responses are correspondingly limited. This section maps the current definitional landscape and identifies the structural limitations of existing approaches.

4. Methodology

This report comprises two components: (1) an overview of the results of a scoping review focusing on the definitions employed in the literature, and (2) a case study illustrating the application and limits of these definitional frameworks in practice. The scoping review maps the conceptual and methodological landscape of SUED research, establishing the conceptual terrain and identifying the structural limits of existing frameworks. The case study, in turn, employs qualitative thematic analysis of long-form video content to examine in detail how extreme discourse circulates within a specific platform environment, providing empirical grounding for these limits and demonstrating what interpretive analysis can reveal that computational approaches cannot.

The scoping review aims to examine the types of language and communication (referred to as *discourse*) used in discussions about migration and ethnic minorities, with a particular focus on narratives that are negative, harmful or divisive. The review was conducted with the support of the AI-assisted platform silvi.ai, which facilitated the systematic coding and analysis of the included articles. These include extreme, radical, hate-filled or polarising discourse, such as

hate speech, Islamophobia, populist rhetoric, xenophobia, racism, toxic framing, disinformation and misinformation. The review also seeks to identify the key actors, institutions, and platforms (e.g., politicians, media organisations, online influencers, social media platforms) that produce or disseminate such discourse. It further investigates the societal impacts and consequences of these narratives and explores the factors that influence susceptibility or resilience among individuals or groups.

A study should be included if it addresses migration-related discourse and focuses on one or more of the following: Linguistic and rhetorical characteristics of extreme or harmful content (e.g., racist tropes, dehumanising metaphors, fear-based narratives); Predictors of and susceptibilities to exposure or acceptance of such content. Relevant contexts may include (but are not limited to): media, education, social media, public communication, and political discourse.

Studies are excluded when they consist of literature reviews, such as systematic reviews, scoping reviews, or other forms of surveys of existing scholarship, rather than original empirical research. Likewise, studies that have been published solely as conference papers in conference proceedings are not considered for inclusion. Publications written in languages other than English are also excluded. Studies are also excluded when their primary focus falls outside the thematic scope of the review. This includes research that does not address discourse that is harmful, extreme, or divisive within a migration-related context. For example, studies that examine violence or racial disparities without establishing a clear link to migration discourse are considered out of scope. Finally, studies that do not concern human migration or the migration-related experiences of ethnic minorities are excluded. Research on topics such as data migration, animal migration, or bird migration therefore does not meet the inclusion criteria. More details on the process of conducting the scoping review are provided elsewhere (Melis et al., 2026).

5. Insights from the Scoping Review

The research reviewed draws on a wide range of quantitative and qualitative methods for studying socially unacceptable extreme discourse on digital platforms. Computational approaches, including large language models, keyword-based classifiers, and supervised machine learning, allow analysis at scale and enable systematic detection across large datasets. Qualitative approaches, including discourse analysis, reflexive thematic analysis, and content analysis of multimodal data, offer interpretive depth and sensitivity to coded or implicit language that quantitative tools tend to miss.

Each approach carries characteristic trade-offs. Computational methods are replicable and scalable but perform poorly on strategically ambiguous content, where meaning is distributed across context rather than concentrated in explicit markers. Qualitative methods capture nuance and coded communication but are resource-intensive and less readily generalisable across contexts and platforms. In practice, the most consequential forms of extreme discourse, including content that operates through implication, euphemism, and cumulative framing, are

precisely those that present the greatest difficulty for automated detection. This methodological gap reinforces the conceptual argument developed in the preceding section: effective analysis of borderline and mainstreamed content requires interpretive approaches capable of engaging with the strategic dimension of the material.

Our scoping review of research on SUEd identifies definitional clusters across the literature. The analysis of the sampled articles (N = 255) reveals a marked diversity in the terminology used to capture problematic or exclusionary communication, with no single standardised vocabulary dominating the field. Instead, authors draw on a range of partially overlapping terms. For example, dehumanising discourse is often identified through metaphors such as “invasion,” “parasites,” or “flood,” while exclusionary or othering discourse is reflected in boundary-marking expressions such as “they don’t belong” or “outsiders.” Threat-based narratives frequently frame migrants as “security risks” or “criminal,” whereas delegitimising discourse employs labels such as “bogus asylum seekers” or “illegal invaders.” Other strands of research focus on stereotyping and generalisation (e.g., “they are all...”), moralised or affective polarisation (e.g., “corrupt” or “disgusting”), or forms of incitement and dangerous speech (e.g., “send them back”). Finally, a subset of studies explicitly addresses strategic disinformation, including false or misleading claims about migrants and coordinated narrative manipulation.

Table 1 summarises key definitional clusters identified in the literature, alongside illustrative expressions and operational criteria as reported across studies. Six recurring clusters can be identified across the literature, each with characteristic operationalisation strategies. The largest and most studied cluster addresses hate speech and discriminatory rhetoric, broadly defined as communication that attacks or degrades individuals on the basis of identity characteristics such as ethnicity, religion, or national origin. Within this cluster, hate speech is most clearly defined in international frameworks. For example, the United Nations describes hate speech as any communication that uses pejorative or discriminatory language with reference to a person or a group based on who they are. Operationalisation typically proceeds through word-list filters using dictionaries of slurs or protected-group terms, or through human-coded content analysis that flags hateful themes in context. A closely related cluster addresses dehumanisation and othering: the depiction of target groups through animal metaphors, scapegoating, or binary in-group and out-group framing. Studies in this cluster frequently identify terms such as “parasites,” “vermin,” or “invasion,” and the use of “us versus them” dichotomies as primary markers, analysed through qualitative discourse analysis or computational dependency parsing. A third cluster addresses incitement to violence and the explicit advocacy of violent action to achieve political or ideological ends. Researchers often operationalise this through frequency counts of violence-related keywords or supervised classifiers trained on known extremist propaganda. Polarising and populist rhetoric constitutes a further cluster: language that frames society in binary terms, positioning a virtuous majority against an elite or out-group enemy. Because such rhetoric is often context-dependent and resists keyword-based detection, most studies identify it through qualitative analysis or sentiment-based minority-majority indicators. A smaller cluster covers extremist ideological narratives, including white nationalist and jihadist doctrine, operationalised through

ideological dictionaries or machine learning models trained on extremist as against mainstream texts. Finally, a comparatively rare but analytically distinctive cluster addresses conspiracy narratives, in which societal change is attributed to a secret hostile agency; researchers typically identify this category through targeted lexicons of conspiracy terms or network analysis of shared content.

A synthesised taxonomy of nine discourse types derived from this analysis is presented in Table 1. While the literature tends to group these phenomena into six broader clusters, our analysis differentiates between distinct discourse types within and across these clusters, based on recurring linguistic markers, framing strategies and operationalisation approaches identified in the reviewed studies. For example, the broad cluster of hate and discriminatory discourse encompasses several distinct types in our taxonomy, including dehumanising, delegitimising and stereotyping discourse, while threat-based and conspiratorial clusters are reflected in categories such as fear-based discourse and strategic disinformation. Categories frequently co-occur within individual studies, and operational criteria across them are rarely standardised, reflecting a field that continues to favour context-sensitive conceptualisation over shared detection frameworks.

Table 1. Taxonomy of extreme discourse definitions, example wording, operational criteria and study counts.

Taxonomy of extreme discourse	Example wording	Operational criteria
Dehumanising discourse	"invasion," "parasites," "vermin," "flood"	Presence of metaphors or labels that deny human status or depict groups as non-human entities; often identified via metaphor analysis or keyword dictionaries
Exclusionary / othering discourse	"they don't belong," "outsiders," "threat to our culture"	Discursive construction of in-group vs out-group boundaries; markers of distancing, boundary-making, or symbolic exclusion
Threat and fear-based discourse	"security risk," "criminal migrants," "they will take over"	Explicit or implicit attribution of danger, risk, or harm to a target group; often linked to affective framing (fear, anxiety)
Delegitimising / derogatory discourse	"bogus asylum seekers," "illegal invaders," "welfare abusers"	Use of labels that question legitimacy, legality, or moral worth; typically operationalised via coding of evaluative language
Stereotyping and generalisation	"they are all...," "typical behavior of..."	Attribution of fixed characteristics to entire groups; identified through generalising statements or categorical claims
Strategic disinformation / manipulation	"false claims about migrants," coordinated narratives	Verifiably false or misleading claims targeting groups; operationalised through factchecking or alignment with known disinformation patterns

Moralised affective polarisation discourse	/ "evil," "corrupt," "disgusting"	Strong moral-emotional language that intensifies polarisation; measured via sentiment or moral-emotion lexicons
Incitement dangerous speech	/ "they should be removed," "fight them," "send them back"	Language that legitimises or calls for harm, exclusion, or violence; often linked to "dangerous speech" frameworks
Cultural or symbolic degradation (abjection)	"dirty," "uncivilised," "backward"	Discursive positioning of groups as inferior or contaminating; often analysed through critical or cultural theory lenses

The definitional diversity mapped the above points to a deeper structural problem: the most consequential forms of socially unacceptable extremist discourse (SUED) extend across and between these categories, resisting stable classification. A critical challenge in addressing SUED online is that the most consequential material often falls below thresholds that would trigger removal. Platforms have developed increasingly sophisticated systems for detecting illegal content, including terrorist material, explicit hate speech, and direct incitement to violence. Yet a growing volume of harmful content falls below these detection thresholds while still contributing to polarisation, erosion of institutional trust, and shifts in what is considered acceptable political discourse.

This form of borderline discourse combines radical claims with civil, quasi-academic, and politically moderate language to legitimise far-right positions and render them as rational elements of an exclusionary but mainstream common sense (Krzyżanowski & Ledin, 2017; Krzyżanowski, 2020). This deliberate ambiguity fundamentally undermines linguistic detection approaches. Content producers deploy what Wodak (2015) terms "calculated ambivalence": communicating different messages to different audiences simultaneously, so that committed followers receive radical content while mainstream audiences encounter nothing that formally violates platform rules. The result is content calibrated to circulate freely within existing governance frameworks while progressively shifting the boundaries of acceptable political speech.

Analysing this dynamic requires a framework for mainstreaming: "the process by which actors, discourses, and attitudes move from marginal positions to more central ones, progressively shifting the boundaries of acceptable political, media, and public debate" (Brown, Mondon & Winter, 2023, p. 164). The Overton window, originally theorised by Joseph P. Overton and developed in subsequent scholarship (Lehman et al., 2018), describes the range of positions acceptable to the mainstream at any given moment. Political actors can deliberately expand this range by consistently advancing ideas at or beyond its current edge, normalising previously extreme positions through sustained advocacy until they enter legitimate debate (Russell, 2006). The subsequent phase is normalisation: formerly unacceptable speech becomes routine and unremarkable, the window shifts, and the process recalibrates for the

next cycle (Wodak, 2020). Together, mainstreaming and normalisation describe a process of incremental boundary erosion that is gradual, cumulative, and self-reinforcing.

Conspiracy theories represent a paradigmatic case of content that causes democratic harm through indirect means. They operate through pattern recognition, connecting disparate information into coherent narratives that attribute complex social phenomena to intentional agency (Butter, 2020). This structural flexibility makes them particularly resilient: disconfirming evidence tends to reinforce rather than undermine the conspiracy framework. Conspiracy narratives function as distributable templates; audiences reconstruct the full ideological message from distributed fragments, such that individual content segments carry no detectable extremist markers while together conveying an extremist argument. The social consequences are documented and wide-ranging: conspiracy beliefs erode institutional trust, reduce prosocial behaviour, and increase polarisation and intergroup conflict, including in relation to institutions and groups entirely unconnected to the theories themselves (van Prooijen, Spadaro & Wang, 2022). Conspiracy narratives pose a threat to democratic cohesion through the cumulative erosion of the social trust on which democratic institutions and public deliberation depend.

The definitional frameworks reviewed above share a common assumption: that extreme content can be identified based on its explicit linguistic features, such as the presence of offensive keywords, direct expressions of hostility, or clearly articulated harmful claims. The following case study presents empirical evidence for why that assumption is insufficient when content is deliberately designed to evade classification, and draws out the implications for platform governance, content moderation, and European regulatory frameworks.

6. Case Study

To illustrate the practical limits of existing definitional frameworks, this report draws on an analysis of 40 German-language YouTube vodcasts published between December 2024 and August 2025, comprising over 50 hours of content drawn from AfD politicians, Identitarian activists, and alternative media figures. To ensure transparency and facilitate replicability, an overview of the sampled vodcasts is provided in Appendix A, including titles, publication dates and source channels.

The analysis focuses on long-form content exceeding 15 minutes, the threshold above which YouTube requires account verification and which captures the filmed conversations, panel discussions, and extended interviews constituting the platform's vodcast ecosystem. Format is an analytically significant variable in this context. Short-form content requires consolidated claims; long-form conversation provides the temporal and rhetorical space for cumulative strategies, allowing individual statements to remain formally defensible while their aggregate effect reconstructs extremist logic. The analysis examined how extreme political content circulates through implication rather than explicit declaration, identifying the discursive strategies that enable such content to enter mainstream political debate while remaining below moderation and classification thresholds.

Analysis identified three primary mechanisms through which extreme political content circulates within long-form YouTube content while remaining below moderation thresholds:

institutional delegitimisation, statistical weaponisation, and deniability engineering. Long-form content provides the conversational space for this full repertoire to unfold. Extended runtime allows all three mechanisms to operate within a single video, a condition the short-form environment cannot support given its requirement for consolidated claims. Individual statements remain formally defensible; their co-presence within extended conversations enables extremist logic to circulate as legitimate political debate. Interestingly, 36 of the 40 videos analysed (90%) include explicit meta-commentary on these strategies, with direct references to Overton window shifts, self-censorship, and platform constraints, confirming that the patterns observed reflect conscious strategic production rather than incidental rhetorical drift.

6.1 Mechanism 1: Institutional Delegitimisation

Across all 40 vodcasts, speakers systematically portray institutions (media, academia, courts, and NGOs) as subordinated to left-liberal or globalist elite interests. This institutional delegitimisation constructs an alternative epistemic landscape in which far-right actors present themselves as the sole credible sources of information on migration and demographic change. The pattern operates cumulatively: dispersed remarks accumulate over the course of extended conversations, constructing a picture of systemic institutional capture that prepares audiences to receive extreme narratives as the rational explanation for a suppressed reality.

Delegitimisation proceeds by constructing “the Left” as a coordinated ideological bloc encompassing politicians, journalists, academics, and NGOs. Academia is presented as the primary site of ideological capture, with universities described as “occupied” spaces whose graduates populate “very, very left leaning” courts, converting education into an ideological pipeline. Media receives particularly intensive attacks with speakers framing the press as deliberately misrepresenting refugee demographics and suppressing reporting on migrant-related violence. NGOs are recast as the logistical infrastructure of a “migration mafia,” networks “disguised with humanitarian motives” who profit from migration flows, reframing humanitarian activity as a mechanism of demographic engineering. The result is a self-reinforcing epistemic framework: radical claims are validated precisely because the institutions that would challenge them are presented as compromised. Institutional delegitimisation functions as a preparatory mechanism, establishing the conditions under which the second mechanism can operate.

6.2 Mechanism 2: Statistical Weaponisation

The second mechanism, present in 39 of 40 videos, is statistical weaponisation. Speakers deploy statistics, demographic projections, and pseudo-scientific rhetoric to lend empirical credibility to extreme narratives about demographic change. Selective data, including crime rates, fertility statistics, and unsourced population projections, is presented with the purpose of normalising demographic anxiety as empirical common sense rather than as ideological claim.

Fertility statistics are used to establish demographic decline as existential crisis: “We have too few children to replace previous generations.” This demographic deficit is then framed as a deliberate policy outcome: “The liberal approach is, we replace the children with migrants,” explicitly articulating the core logic of population substitution. Present-day school demographics are offered as confirmation that this substitution is already underway: “Already more than half of first graders have migration background.” Crime statistics serve to translate abstract demographic projections into immediate civilisational threat, with speakers stripping contextual information to present statistical correlation as direct causation. Statistical weaponisation exemplifies what Sedgwick (2024) terms “apparent plausibility”: mathematical projections about differential birth rates are presented with apparent scientific rigour, through data visualisations and selective citations, so that alarmist conclusions acquire the surface quality of sober analysis. This apparent empirical credibility provides, in Sedgwick’s terms, “respectable cover for xenophobia,” enabling the articulation of racialised anxieties in ostensibly neutral demographic language.

6.3 Mechanism 3: Deniability Engineering

Where the first two mechanisms construct the extreme narrative, deniability engineering enables its distribution. Present in 37 of the 40 videos under study, this mechanism comprises a repertoire of positioning strategies: centrist self-presentation to reframe radical positions as principled opposition; dismissal of extremist labels as overused political instruments; and systematic substitution of euphemistic language for legally or socially prosecutable terms. Speakers describe themselves as “conservative” rather than “extremist” and treat accusations of fascism or Nazism as conceptually exhausted: “All these terms right-wing, fascist, Nazi have no value anymore.” Such disclaimers serve to distance speakers from stigmatised categories while repositioning radical content as legitimate political dissent.

Euphemistic redefinition renders radical policies publicly communicable. The “remigration” case illustrates the mechanism: AfD politicians define remigration as making “voluntary return attractive” rather than as forced deportation, reframing a policy of compulsory removal as a form of benevolence. These substitutions operate as coded signals, communicating radical intent to sympathetic audiences while maintaining surface respectability for broader public and institutional scrutiny. Cultural and civilisational framing applies the same substitution logic to demographic discourse: speakers frame anxieties about demographic change in cultural rather than biological terms, replacing racial categories with values-based ones, as in the formulation “It’s not skin colour, it’s values.” Discussions open with ostensibly neutral questions about integration before moving to claims of inherent incompatibility, “parallel societies,” and eventual warnings of democratic collapse. Racial arguments are preserved in substance while being repackaged in a register that avoids formal classification as extremist content.

Those three mechanisms form an integrated system. Institutional delegitimation removes credibility from sources that might challenge extreme narratives. Statistical weaponisation constructs an alternative empirical foundation. Deniability engineering ensures that individual statements remain formally defensible under existing platform rules and legal frameworks. The

systemic quality of this architecture is central to its governance implications: fragment-level content moderation, which evaluates individual statements in isolation, is structurally ill-suited to content designed to operate through cumulative effect. No individual statement carries the extreme claim; the claim is produced by the relations between statements, and this is precisely what fragment-level moderation cannot see.

6.4 Evidence of Strategic Intent: Meta-Awareness

What distinguishes this dataset is the open theorisation by speakers of their own communication strategies. Across 36 of 40 videos, speakers discuss censorship, moderation thresholds, and the Overton window, coach peers on effective formulations, and mark progress in what can now be said in public. One AfD politician declares his aim "to expand the speech corridors and shift the so-called Overton window" (V10); another credits a peer for teaching him to "describe things a bit more politically correctly" (V14); a third jokes about labelling inflammatory remarks as satire, a "little anticipatory obedience" (V06) calibrated to Germany's incitement laws. This reflexive dimension transforms analytical inference into documented evidence: mainstreaming operates here as a deliberate curriculum transmitted through established networks, rather than as drift.

Explicit references to the Overton window offer direct evidence of intentional boundary-shifting. Speakers track shifts in public legitimacy as collective achievements, with one noting that "we are winning this political battle... the winning side is clearly the right" (V27) and frame the growing acceptability of topics like remigration as confirmation that the window has moved. Within this boundary work, they actively manage legal and platform constraints: discussing how to avoid giving Germany's domestic intelligence service "any excuse" (V06), referencing the labelling of inflammatory remarks as satire, and employing performative self-censorship by halting mid-sentence with "Do I have to bleep that out now?" (V32). This signals awareness of YouTube moderation thresholds while simultaneously framing suppressed statements as prohibited truths.

Platform literacy is transmitted as shared professional knowledge. Speakers compare formulations that continue to pass YouTube moderation and explicitly attribute effective language to peer guidance: "He gave me a tip... describe things a bit more politically correctly." Experienced creators mentor newcomers, transmitting methods for preserving radical substance within algorithmically viable formats. As one speaker summarises: "You can self-censor without losing edge." Mainstreaming is a technique developed and transmitted within far-right networks, calibrated to the specific governance constraints of individual platforms.

7. Conclusion and Recommendations

This report has examined socially unacceptable extreme discourse (SUED) from two complementary perspectives: a scoping review of existing definitional and methodological approaches, and a case study of how extreme content circulates in practice in long-form German-language YouTube vodcasts. Together, these two components illuminate both the current state of the research field and the structural limits of existing governance frameworks when confronted with content that is deliberately calibrated to evade them.

The scoping review establishes that the research literature has produced a rich but fragmented taxonomy of extreme discourse. Six recurring definitional clusters were identified, covering hate speech, incitement to violence, dehumanisation, conspiracy narratives, polarising rhetoric, and extremist ideology. Definitions are jurisdiction-specific, methodologically diverse and frequently overlapping. The methodological landscape reflects this fragmentation: computational approaches offer detection at scale but struggle with strategically ambiguous content, while qualitative approaches capture nuance but are resource-intensive and difficult to scale. No single method is adequate to the full range of content that contributes to democratic harm, and the most consequential borderline content consistently falls into the gaps between existing approaches.

The case study provides empirical grounding for what the conceptual literature describes as borderline and mainstreamed discourse. Three integrated mechanisms were identified across 40 German-language vodcasts: institutional delegitimation, which removes credibility from sources capable of challenging extreme narratives; statistical weaponisation, which constructs an alternative empirical foundation for demographic anxiety; and deniability engineering, which ensures that individual statements remain formally defensible under platform rules and legal frameworks while their cumulative effect reconstructs extremist logic. That 90 percent of the sample includes explicit meta-commentary on these strategies confirms that mainstreaming operates as a deliberate and transmissible technique, not as incidental rhetorical drift. The long-form video format is central to how this operates: extended runtime provides the conversational space for all three mechanisms to unfold within a single piece of content; a condition that short-form environments structurally preclude.

These findings converge on a structural observation: existing governance frameworks, at both platform and regulatory levels, are calibrated to detect content by what it explicitly states. The content most urgently requiring governance operates through accumulation, implication, and deliberate exploitation of definitional gaps. The EU's Digital Services Act offers the most developed response, extending beyond illegal content through its systemic risk provisions (Articles 34 and 35), which oblige Very Large Online Platforms to identify and mitigate risks to fundamental rights, civic discourse, and public security. Recital 84 explicitly brings legal-but-harmful content within scope, and the integration of the Codes of Conduct on Hate Speech (January 2025) and Disinformation (July 2025) into the DSA framework converts previously voluntary commitments into compliance benchmarks. Yet this architecture remains structurally misaligned with the content examined here. Systemic risk is definitionally underspecified, with platforms, auditors, and Digital Services Coordinators operating with divergent methodologies. Articles 34(2) and 35 direct regulatory attention toward algorithmic amplification rather than toward the discursive construction of what is amplified, allowing compliance to be demonstrated through engagement metrics without engaging the semiotic work through which content gains its political effect. The co-regulatory turn has also proven vulnerable to strategic withdrawal, with signatories reducing Code commitments by 31 percent between 2022 and 2025. Addressing cumulative, implicational content requires governance approaches sensitive to aggregate effect, format-specific in calibration, and capable of integrating interpretive analysis alongside computational detection; it also requires sharper

definitional benchmarks within the DSA's systemic risk framework, so that the discursive production of harm becomes as legible to regulators as its algorithmic distribution.

7.1 Recommendations

Recommendation 1: Develop a shared operational framework for borderline extreme discourse.

The scoping review identifies six overlapping definitional clusters but no cross-jurisdictional consensus on what constitutes extreme discourse below explicit illegality thresholds. Effective platform governance and regulatory harmonisation across Member States require a shared operational framework that addresses borderline and mainstreamed content, not only content that meets existing legal definitions of hate speech or incitement. Such a framework should be developed iteratively, in dialogue with research communities, platforms and civil society organisations.

Recommendation 2: Invest in hybrid detection infrastructure.

The scoping review documents a persistent methodological gap: computational tools are scalable but structurally limited in detecting content that operates through implication, coded language, and cumulative framing, while qualitative approaches offer depth but cannot scale to platform-level volumes. Research and governance investment should be directed towards hybrid infrastructure that integrates interpretive analysis with computational detection, rather than treating these as alternatives. Funding frameworks, including Horizon Europe research programmes, should reflect this need.

Recommendation 3: Incorporate content format as an independent moderation variable.

Long-form video affords strategic repertoires that short-form content structurally forecloses. Moderation frameworks and algorithmic governance criteria calibrated to short-form or text-based content transfer poorly to long-form video environments. Platform governance frameworks should treat format as an independent analytical variable, with extended-runtime content subject to criteria that account for how strategic ambiguity accumulates over time.

Recommendation 4: Map cross-platform mainstreaming infrastructure.

Both the scoping review and the case study indicate that extreme discourse operates within ecosystems: recommendation networks, cross-promotion between channels, and peer transmission of effective formulations. Governance responses focused on individual pieces of content or individual actors are likely to be insufficient. Systematic mapping of algorithmic and social connections between actors within and across platforms is needed to understand the infrastructure through which mainstreaming strategies are coordinated and transmitted.

Recommendation 5: Address the social trust dimension of conspiracy-based discourse.

The scoping review documents that conspiracy narratives erode institutional trust and reduce prosocial behaviour at the societal level, including in relation to institutions entirely unconnected to the conspiracy content. Governance responses focused exclusively on the removal of individual pieces of content are insufficient to address these systemic effects. Policy frameworks should be complemented by investment in media literacy, institutional transparency, and public communication strategies that address the conditions in which conspiracy narratives gain traction.

8. References

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9. Appendix

Corpus of 40 German-language vodcasts (December 2024 to August 2025) analysed for the study. Each entry details title, duration, channel, guest profile and publication date. Speakers were categorised by Actor Type based on institutional constraints and legitimacy sources, capturing the ecosystem's heterogeneity and explaining variation in mainstreaming strategy deployment.

Actor Type Categories

Category	Definition	n
Formal Political Actors	AfD politicians, candidates, and party-adjacent figures operating under electoral, legal, and party discipline constraints	9
Movement Activists	Identitarian movement members and explicitly far-right activists already under stigmatisation	5
Institutional Defectors	Former or current police, lawyers, and state employees leveraging institutional credentials in alternative media	3
Platform-Native Creators	YouTube-first personalities whose primary constraint is algorithmic rather than institutional	10
Intellectual Legitimisers	Published authors, former elite journalists, and academics providing cerebral legitimisation	6
Crossover Amplifiers	Finance YouTubers, entertainers, and lifestyle figures who entered political commentary from non-political domains	7

Corpus Table

ID	Title	Channel	Guest	Date	Duration	Actor Type	Description
V01	Deutschland im Würgegriff eines Kaders	Tichys Einblick	Roland Tichy	2025-08-09	29:41	Intellectual Legitimiser	Former Wirtschaftswoche editor-in-chief; founded Tichys Einblick
V02	Deutsch sein ist kein Verbrechen	Alexander Bieber	Matthias Helferich	2025-04-07	1:12:57	Formal Political Actor	AfD Bundestag member (NRW); völkisch wing; "friendly face of NS" scandal
V03	Der Wandel kommt nicht friedlich	Alexander Bieber	Schattenmacher	2025-07-25	1:23:00	Platform-Native Creator	Anonymous YouTube commentator; Honigwabe podcast; IfS-adjacent
V04	Europa wird systematisch zerstört	Max Otte	Flavio von Witzleben	2025-01-02	57:39	Platform-Native Creator	Former RT DE correspondent; pro-Russia YouTube channel
V05	Thilo Sarrazin über Migration	Meet Your Mentor	Thilo Sarrazin	2025-03-30	1:15:34	Intellectual Legitimiser	Former Berlin Finance Senator; Bundesbank board; SPD expelled 2020
V06	Es geht um Deutschland und meine Kinder	Alexander Bieber	Arminius	2025-07-18	52:41	Movement Activist	Identitarian activist operating under pseudonym

V07	Martin Sellner im Gespräch	Politik Spezial	Martin Sellner	2025-07-30	32:08	Movement Activist	IBÖ co-founder; "Remigration" architect; Potsdam meeting presenter
V08	Merkel zerstörte Deutschland	Kettner-Edelmetalle	Gerald Grosz	2025-08-03	42:06	Crossover Amplifier	Former Austrian BZÖ politician; media performer; 2022 presidential candidate
V09	Passen Sie sich der Fließrichtung an	Kanal Schnellroda	Maximilian Krahn	2025-06-09	1:40:58	Formal Political Actor	AfD Bundestag (Saxony direct mandate); former EU lead candidate
V10	Das verbotene Gespräch mit Sellner	freiformation	Martin Sellner	2025-07-13	1:46:53	Movement Activist	IBÖ co-founder; platform-banned; entry bans UK, USA, Switzerland
V11	So wird unsere Heimat ruiniert	Unspecified	Sylvia Pantel	2025-02-08	3:27:46	Formal Political Actor	Former CDU Bundestag (2013–2021); Werteunion deputy federal chair
V12	Afghanen strömen nach Deutschland	Krautzone	Florian Müller & Boris Morgenstern	2025-03-09	1:01:02	Platform-Native Creator	Krautzone magazine founders; "libertär-konservativ" positioning
V13	Albtraum Grenzenlosigkeit	NuoFlix	Boekard Voß	2025-04-22	42:20	Intellectual Legitimiser	Author and intellectual

V1 4	Basierter Reise- YouTuber	Jasmin Kosubek	Freiformatio n	202 5- 06- 01	1:21:3 7	Moveme nt Activist	Travel YouTuber turned migration critic; ideological network ties
V1 5	Dara ZERSTÖRT die neue Migrationsdoku	KetzerKir che	Critical Cat	202 5- 04- 28	1:57:5 8	Platform- Native Creator	Former SWR employee; ÖRR criticism focus; Kontrafunk contributor
V1 6	Deutschland ist nicht sicher!	Marc Friedrich	Manuel Ostermann	202 5- 05- 17	51:53	Institutio nal Defector	Active Bundespolizei officer; DPoIG deputy federal chair
V1 7	Deutschland schafft sich ab	Kettner- Edelmetal le	Thilo Sarrazin	202 5- 07- 23	48:17	Intellectu al Legitimise r	Deutschland schafft sich ab author (1.5M copies sold)
V1 8	Deutschland scheitert	Unspecifi ed	Marc Friedrich	202 5- 07- 16	2:33:4 2	Crossov er Amplifier	Finance author; "Crash Prophet"; 662K YouTube subscribers
V1 9	Die große Integrationslüge	Krautzone	Müller & Morgenstern	202 5- 06- 17	1:01:2 7	Platform- Native Creator	Krautzone hosts
V2 0	Die Macht der Sprache	Junge Freiheit	Kolja Barghoorn	202 4- 12- 23	43:00	Crossov er Amplifier	"Aktien mit Kopf" finance YouTuber; post-2022 political pivot
V2 1	Die unfassbare Wahrheit über Deutschland	Kettner- Edelmetal le	Philip Hopf	202 5- 05- 21	22:34	Crossov er Amplifier	Hoss & Hopf co- host; finance analyst background

V2 2	Georg Restle und die Zahlen	KetzerKir che	HirstattHetz e	202 5- 05- 02	1:51:3 3	Platform- Native Creator	Anonymous YouTube commentator; anti-ÖRR reaction content
V2 3	Freibad-Terror & Justizskandale	Politik Spezial	Markus Haintz	202 5- 07- 03	40:24	Institutio nal Defector	Lawyer; Querdenken co- founder; "Anwälte für Aufklärung"
V2 4	Ich kämpfe um meine Heimat	Alexander Bieber	Martin Kohler	202 5- 02- 09	2:31:0 8	Formal Political Actor	AfD Berlin district assembly; former Junge Alternative chair
V2 5	Kinder statt Inder	Krautzone	Müller & Morgenstern	202 5- 08- 03	1:02:4 7	Platform- Native Creator	Krautzone hosts
V2 6	Kommt die Migrationswend e?	Krautzone	Müller & Morgenstern	202 5- 04- 13	1:06:0 0	Platform- Native Creator	Krautzone hosts
V2 7	Maximilian Krah über Macht & Tabus	Meet Your Mentor	Maximilian Krah	202 5- 02- 20	2:15:3 2	Formal Political Actor	AfD Bundestag; Antaios author; IfS regular
V2 8	Monika Gruber über die Bundestagswahl	Schuler! Fragen, was ist	Monika Gruber	202 5- 02- 20	42:11	Crossov er Amplifier	Bavarian cabaret artist; COVID-era political commentary pivot
V2 9	Neues aus der Asylindustrie	KetzerKir che	Schonungslo s	202 5- 07- 21	53:11	Platform- Native Creator	YouTube-native commentator

V3 0	Olga Petersen im Exil	Alexander von Bismarck	Olga Petersen	202 5- 07- 30	1:25:3 6	Formal Political Actor	Former AfD Hamburg; mandate revoked Dec 2024; expelled; fled to Russia
V3 1	Realitätsschock Afghanistan	Junge Freiheit	Freiformatio n	202 5- 05- 28	55:13	Moveme nt Activist	Travel YouTuber with Identitarian network positioning
V3 2	Rechtsaktivist & YouTuber Aron P.	Jasmin Kosubek	Aron P. / Shlomo Finkelstein	202 5- 07- 06	1:33:5 9	Platform- Native Creator	Die Vulgäre Analyse; convicted Volksverhetzung 2020
V3 3	Schock in Afghanistan	Eingast	Freiformatio n	202 5- 06- 24	1:00:0 5	Moveme nt Activist	Travel YouTuber with Identitarian network positioning
V3 4	Migration außer Kontrolle	Flavio von Witzleben	Enxhi Seli- Zacharias & Anna Nguyen	202 5- 07- 27	1:04:4 0	Formal Political Actor	AfD Landtag members (NRW, Hessen); "diverse faces" strategic pairing
V3 5	Wisnewski Aktuell #4	NuoFlix	Gerhard Wisnewski	202 5- 01- 26	43:10	Intellectu al Legitimis er	Former WDR journalist; conspiracy author; Grimme Prize 2000
V3 6	Ex-Polizist: Ausländerkrimin alität	Unspecifi ed	Eloy Quent	202 5- 03- 22	2:34:0 1	Institutio nal Defector	Former police officer
V3 7	WOKE- Wahnsinn / Aufarbeitung / Wahlen	Marc Friedrich	Monika Gruber	202 5- 02- 15	1:28:3 5	Crossov er Amplifier	Bavarian cabaret artist; Bavarian Order of Merit 2019

V3 8	Als Migranten-Tochter in der AfD	Eingast	Anna Nguyen	202 5- 08- 13	57:14	Formal Political Actor	AfD Landtag Hessen; Vietnamese refugee parents; strategic diversity figure
V3 9	Aschaffenburg... jetzt reicht's!	Hoss & Hopf	Philip Hopf & Kiarash Hossainpour	202 5- 01- 24	45:50	Crossover Amplifier	Hoss & Hopf hosts; top German podcast; finance-to-politics pipeline
V4 0	Die Sonntag Runde mit Müller-Ullrich	Kontrafunk	Burkhard Müller-Ullrich et al.	202 5- 06- 08	53:43	Intellectual Legitimiser	Former Deutschlandfunk/SWR; Kontrafunk founder

Note. Video URLs withheld to maintain reviewer anonymity and avoid directing traffic toward far-right content creators. Actor Type categories reflect speakers' primary institutional positioning and constraint structures; some speakers occupy boundary positions (noted in descriptions).